

SCHOOL LEARNING ACTION CELL (SLAC) IMPLEMENTATION AND ITS IMPACT ON THE PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF ARLING PANLIPUNAN TEACHERS

Karen Kaye B. Erfe ¹, Mary Grace O. Gallego, PhD. ²

¹*Araling Panlipunan Department, Sto. Niño National High School, Sto. Niño, South Cotabato, Philippines*

²*School of Graduate Studies, Sultan Kudarat State University, EJC Montilla, Tacurong City, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) is a school-based professional learning community designed for the development of teachers, mandated by the Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines. This study sought to evaluate the level of SLAC implementation and its impact on the professional development of Araling Panlipunan teachers in Sto. Niño District, Sto. Niño, South Cotabato. A descriptive and correlational research design was used in this study, and 34 Proficient (Teacher I- III) secondary Araling Panlipunan teachers were considered respondents. Due to their limited number, the total enumeration sampling technique was used to select the teacher-respondents. Frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, Pearson r moment correlation and One- way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), t-test, and Tukey- Kramer Multiple Comparison tests were used to analyze the data. Findings revealed that The SLAC is fully implemented in secondary schools in the district in terms of content and pedagogy, content assessment, ICT integration and 21st century skills and curriculum contextualization with no significant difference in the level of implementation. Furthermore, SLAC had a very strong impact on the Professional Development of Araling Panlipunan teachers in terms of pedagogical, personal, social, and professional competence. The impact of SLAC implementation on the Personal Competence of teachers is slightly lower yet remains highly significant. Moreover, the level of SLAC

implementation has a strong relationship with the professional development of Araling Panlipunan teachers. The age, the teaching experience, and the classroom observation ratings of the respondents also had a significant influence on the professional development and SLAC implementation.

Keywords: *School Learning Action Cell, Professional Development, Proficient teachers*

INTRODUCTION

In an era characterized by rapid globalization and technological advancements, education systems worldwide face the pressing challenge of adapting to evolving pedagogical demands. This includes the quality of instruction, where teachers, as agents of change and education, must possess the perseverance to acquire new skills and adjust to emerging trends.

Additionally, in a world where knowledge is essential, a teacher must deal with new kinds of cooperation, collaboration, and new ways of obtaining knowledge in a networked environment. Teaching in a knowledge-based culture requires these new skills (Suri, 2016).

In recent years, the Philippines' education changes have placed greater importance on teachers' collaborative learning and professional development. One such initiative is the DepEd Order 35 series 2016, which creates the School Learning Action Cell (LAC) as a K–12 basic education program and school-based ongoing professional development plan. This school-based professional learning community aims to enhance teaching strategies and increase student learning outcomes.

SLACs also foster teamwork, collaboration, continuous learning, and innovation among teachers. They provide opportunities for teachers to share best practices, discuss instructional challenges, and collectively develop strategies to improve their teaching delivery. According to Binauhan's (2019) research, training and development programs like the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) give teachers the attitudes, abilities, and knowledge they need to perform well.

In the context of Araling Panlipunan, effective teaching is a crucial subject in shaping students' understanding of history, culture, society, and governance. The quality of teaching in Social Studies affects how students grasp complex concepts and influences their critical thinking and problem-solving skills. However, many teachers face challenges such as outdated teaching methods, limited resources, and a lack of professional development opportunities, which can negatively impact student learning outcomes.

The School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) offers a potential solution to these challenges by providing a platform for Araling Panlipunan teachers to collaborate, reflect, refine their teaching practices, and develop professionally. This research aims to investigate the level of SLAC implementation and how it affects the professional

development of secondary Araling Panlipunan teachers in Sto. District, Sto. Niño, South Cotabato, since not all schools implementing SLAC are tracked and assessed regularly.

Additionally, the study can shed light on the role of SLAC in fostering meaningful changes in teachers' performance, offering guidance for school administrators and policymakers to refine teacher development programs further.

Research Questions

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. educational attainment;
 - 1.4. teaching experience in years during the SLAC implementation, and
 - 1.5. classroom Observation ratings for the last three years (2021-2024) during SLAC implementation?
2. What is the level of implementation of SLAC among teachers in the areas of:
 - 2.1. content and pedagogy;
 - 2.2. content assessment;
 - 2.3. 21st-century skills and ICT integration in teaching Araling Panlipunan; and
 - 2.4. curriculum contextualization as rated by the respondents?
3. What is the perceived impact of SLAC Implementation on the Professional Development of the respondents in the areas of:
 - 3.1. pedagogical competence;
 - 3.2. personal competence;
 - 3.3. social competence; and
 - 3.4. professional competence?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of SLAC Implementation in the areas of:
 - 4.1. content and pedagogy;
 - 4.2. content assessment;
 - 4.3. 21st-century skills and ICT integration in teaching Araling Panlipunan; and
 - 4.4. curriculum contextualization as rated by the respondents?
5. Is there a significant difference between the perceived impact of SLAC implementation in the Professional Development of Araling Panlipunan teachers in terms of:
 - 5.1. pedagogical competence;
 - 5.2. personal competence;
 - 5.3. social competence; and
 - 5.4. professional competence?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the SLAC implementation level and its perceived impact on the professional development of Araling Panlipunan teachers?
7. Is the Demographic profile of the Araling Panlipunan teachers significantly influential on their Professional Development and the SLAC Implementation?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized descriptive and correlational research design. It aims to examine and describe the relationship between various factors in a manner other than a cause-and-effect one (Clarete et al., 2023).

This study used a descriptive design to describe the demographic profile of the respondents, the level of implementation of the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC), and the perceived impact of the SLAC implementation on the Professional Development of secondary Araling Panlipunan teachers in Sto. Niño District, Sto. Niño, South Cotabato. Salaria (2012) defines descriptive research as gathering information about prevailing conditions or situations for description and interpretation.

Also, it utilized the correlation analysis method, using statistical analysis to investigate how strongly two continuous variables were related. This can be applied to the School Learning Action Cell and the Professional Development of Araling Panlipunan teachers. This analysis is useful because the researcher wants to determine the relationships between the variables.

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted in Sto. Niño District in the Municipality of Sto. Niño located in the Province of South Cotabato. The municipality is a lone district with 12 (twelve) elementary schools and 5 (five) secondary schools implementing the School Learning Action Cell. The said district claimed to be one of the top-performing districts in the province.

The researcher was also interested in the study setting since she works as an Araling Panlipunan teacher in one of the district's secondary schools. Specifically, the researcher conducted the study in secondary schools, where she found that SLAC programs and activities were not tracked and assessed regularly and were not yet recognized by the Professional Regulatory Commission (PRC), unlike in elementary schools, where teacher participants in SLAC sessions were able to gain Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Units.

In terms of topography, the location of the schools was very accessible to transportation by focusing also on a specific geographic area, like Sto. Niño District, the research can address the unique context, challenges, and opportunities within this community (Creswell & Creswell, 2017).

Respondents of the Study

The study's respondents were secondary Proficient (Teacher I-III) Araling Panlipunan public school teachers in the Sto. Niño District, Sto. Niño, South Cotabato. They were all regular personnel based on the plantilla items who were at least three (3)

years in service. The researcher considered a population of thirty-four (34) teachers participating in SLAC sessions.

Table 1. No. of Araling Panlipunan Teachers/ Respondents of the study

School	No. Proficient Araling Panlipunan Teachers
Sto. Niño National High School	18
Panay National High School	6
Katipunan National High School	5
Guinsang- an National High School	3
Sto. Niño School of Arts and Trade	2
Total	34

Sampling Technique

Due to the limited number of Araling Panlipunan respondents, complete enumeration was employed to determine them. According to Abrol (2021), information was collected from every member of the population in a complete enumeration census. Furthermore, complete enumeration sampling was used when the small population shared well-defined features, such as those in Proficient Araling Panlipunan teachers with direct experiences and participation in SLAC sessions.

Data Gathering Instrument

The researcher adopted and modified the questionnaire to gather the relevant data for the study through teachers' responses. The content was derived from readings of related literature and studies by Delos Santos (2023) on the School Learning Action Cell and Competencies of Elementary Teachers and Dealala and Lopez (2024) on the School Learning Action Cell Implementation and its impact on the personal and professional development among elementary teachers.

The questionnaire had three parts. Part I focused on the demographic profile of the respondents, including their age, sex, educational attainment, years in service during the SLAC implementation, and Classroom Observation Ratings for the last three (3) years (S.Y. 2021- 2024). Part II consisted of items on the level of SLAC implementation among teachers in Content and Pedagogy, Content Assessment, 21st-century Skills, ICT Integration, and Curriculum Contextualization among Araling Panlipunan teachers in Sto. Niño District.

Part III focused on the respondents' perceptions of the SLAC implementation's impact on their professional development in pedagogical, personal, social, and professional competence.

The Results-based Performance Management System (RPMS) evaluation process includes the Classroom Observation Ratings of Proficient Araling Panlipunan

teachers. According to DepEd Memo No. 004, s. 2022 & DepEd Memo No. 008, s. 2023, this tool was used for assessing teachers' proficiency on seven (7) indicators with a COT rating and a transmuted RPMS rating of: 7–5 (outstanding), 6- 4 (very- satisfactory), 5- 3 (satisfactory), 4- 2 (unsatisfactory), and 3- 1 (poor).

To analyze the level of implementation of School Learning Action Cells (SLAC) in terms of content and pedagogy, content assessment, 21st-century skills and ICT integration, and curriculum contextualization, a five (5) point Likert scale was used where 5 corresponds to always, 4 to often, 3 to sometimes, 2 to rarely, and 1 to never.

To analyze the perceived impact of School Learning Action Cell Implementation on the Professional Growth and Development of Araling Panlipunan regarding Pedagogical, Personal, Social, and Professional competence, a five (5) point Likert Scale was also used where 5 corresponds to strongly agree, 4 to agree, 3 to undecided, 2 disagree, and 1 to strongly disagree.

Krosnick and Fabrigar (1997) recommend using a five-point (5) itemized rating scale as a more reliable rating scale. When a midpoint is included, the effects of responder bias tend to diminish, and data quality is enhanced.

The researcher asked permission from the School Heads to utilize the teachers' COT ratings for the study. The respondents also signed a data privacy consent form.

Furthermore, a validity test was performed to ensure the instrument measured what it intended to measure. Five (5) evaluators: three (3) Master Teachers and SLAC Leaders, and two (2) Curriculum experts validated the study instruments. To ensure the instructions were clear and the study's goals were fulfilled, these subject-matter experts critically evaluated the instrument. Scale content validation (S-CVI) and item content validation (I-CVI) indices were calculated. The researcher used an acceptable CVI of 1 (Yusoff, 2019).

Moreover, a reliability test was conducted using the instrument's internal consistency method based on the results of pilot testing. According to Creswell and Creswell (2018), reliability is the extent to which the study methodology produces steady and consistent outcomes. Additionally, a measure was considered reliable if it had the same result when applied to the same measurement item several times. The Cronbach alpha was computed to determine the reliability of the research instrument used in this study. The tool's reliability was facilitated through a pilot test in secondary schools in Norala District, South Cotabato. The result of the reliability test was 0.97804, which was considered excellent.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study focused on implementing the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) and its impact on the professional development of Araling Panlipunan teachers in Sto. Niño District, Sto. Niño, South Cotabato. The geographical scope was limited to this region, providing a context-specific analysis. The study involves all secondary schools and all

secondary Proficient (Teacher I-III) Araling Panlipunan teachers in Sto. Niño District, South Cotabato Division. Master Teachers were not included as respondents since they are categorized as Highly Proficient teachers who demonstrate a high level of performance in their teaching practice, perform classroom observations, and provide technical assistance to Proficient teachers (DepEd Order No. 2, series of 2015).

The participants were chosen based on specific criteria to ensure relevance to the research objectives. The study was time-bounded to the year SY 2016-2024, which covered the years of implementation of the SLAC, assessing the level of Implementation and its perceived impact on the professional development of Araling Panlipunan teachers. The research questions were adopted and modified to address the relationship between the SLAC and teachers' professional development within the defined scope.

Statistical Treatment

This study used several statistical treatments to present, analyze, and interpret the data. Statistical treatment is essential for using data in the right form. The responses from the completed questionnaires and classroom observation ratings were properly encoded, processed, and analyzed using Microsoft Excel software. The data were computed using the appropriate statistical tools.

The data were treated using frequency counts and percentage distributions for the respondents' profiles. The mean was computed to analyze the level of Implementation of SLAC in different areas and its perceived impact on the respondents' professional development in different areas.

The one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was utilized to analyze the differences in the Level of Implementation of SLAC in Content and Pedagogy, Content Assessment, 21st-century skills, ICT integration, and Curriculum Contextualization as rated by the respondents. It was also used to analyze the differences in the impact of SLAC on the professional development of Araling Panlipunan teachers in terms of pedagogical competence, personal competence, social competence, and professional competence. The Tukey-Kramer Multiple Comparison test was also used to determine which professional development component has the highest impact on SLAC implementation.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation or Pearson r Correlation was employed to analyze the significant relationship between the SLAC Implementation level and the perceived impact on the Professional Development of Araling Panlipunan teachers. The use of Pearson r correlation allows for the testing of statistical significance. It is crucial to determine whether any observed correlation between the extent of SLAC implementation and the perceived impact of SLAC Implementation is likely to be due to chance or if it reflects a genuine relationship (Field, 2013).

RESULTS

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 2. Demographic Profile of the Respondents according to Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
28-32	14	41
33-37	9	26
38-42	4	12
43-47	5	15
48-52	1	3
53-57	1	3
Total	34	100

Table 3. Demographic Profile of the Respondents according to Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	12	35
Female	22	65
Total	34	100

Table 4. Demographic Profile of the Respondents According to Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Bachelor's Degree	6	18
With Master's Units	24	70
Master's Degree	3	9
With Doctorate Units	1	3
With Doctorate Degree	0	0
Total	34	100

Table 5. Demographic Profile of the Respondents According to Years in Service during SLAC Implementation

Years in Service	Frequency	Percentage (%)
3	4	12
4	1	3
5	2	6
6	6	17
7	5	15
8	16	47
Total	34	100

Table 6. Demographic Profile of the Respondents According to Ratings on Classroom Observations from 2021- 2024

School Year	SD	Mean	Description
2021-2022	0.11	4.79	Outstanding
2022-2023	0.12	4.80	Outstanding
2023-2024	0.11	4.80	Outstanding
Overall Mean		4.80	Outstanding

Level of SLAC Implementation

Table 7. Level of Implementation of SLAC in the Area of Content and Pedagogy

Indicator	Mean	Description
The School Learning Action Cell....		
1. includes contents that enhances teachers' understanding of the Matatag and K to 12 Curriculum in preparation for their Araling Panlipunan lessons.	4.44	Always
2. focuses on key curriculum areas.	4.44	Always
3. ensures teachers' mastery of content and performance standards.	4.38	Always
4. ensures the alignment of instructional materials with learning standards.	4.50	Always
5. enables teachers, master teachers and school heads to craft jointly learning goals fostering collaboration and peer feedbacks among them through LAC sessions.	4.41	Always
6. assists teachers to plan weekly Araling Panlipunan lessons, which can be implemented for a specified period.	4.29	Always

7. encourages teachers to use student-centered and inquiry based approaches, differentiated instruction and technology integration in teaching and learning.	4.59	Always
8. promotes the use of different developmentally appropriate teaching methods that respect the individual differences of learners.	4.56	Always
9. allows refinement in teaching resources and materials for specific content areas.	4.51	Always
10. addresses the challenges encountered in delivering Araling Panlipunan lessons.	4.35	Always
Section Mean	4.43	Always

Table 8. Level of implementation of SLAC in the area of Content and Assessment

Indicator	Mean	Description
The School Learning Action Cell....		
1. implements the learner-centered assessment policies based on Matatag and K- 12 Curriculum.	4.53	Always
2. sets a target for desired learning in every classes and grading period.	4.44	Always
3. reviews assessments to ensure its alignment with learning objectives and standards.	4.24	Always
4. ensures that assessments used by teachers are organized and measures higher order thinking skills.	4.41	Always
5. involves teachers in the review and revision of assessment rubrics and scoring to ensure its clarity and consistency.	4.26	Always
6. provides teachers with resources and materials to support assessment development and implementation.	4.32	Always
7. uses the results of assessments to address diverse needs of students.	4.32	Always
8. identifies the trends and gaps of students learning through assessment results.	4.38	Always
9. interprets student performance data from assessments conducted to identify any improvements in content- specific learning outcomes.	4.29	Always
10. plans and gives appropriate feed backing of students' academic performances and	4.35	Always

results with their parents to identify the areas for improvement, and where students need to be further assisted or extended.

Section Mean	4.36	Always
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Table 9. Level of Implementation of SLAC in the area of 21st-Century Skills and ICT Integration

Indicator	Mean	Description
The School Learning Action Cell....		
1. brings 21 st Century Skills into teaching and learning situations as a central feature of the Matatag and K to 12 Curriculum.	4.59	Always
2. encourages the use of teaching strategies that will foster problem solving and decision making skills in students.	4.59	Always
3. promotes group works and collaborative projects that foster leadership, responsibility and effective communication for both teachers and students	4.59	Always
4. provides learning opportunities for students to foster their creativity and innovation.	4.68	Always
5. utilizes ICT developmentally for learners.	4.53	Always
6. makes instruction and assessment processes more collaborative with ICT.	4.32	Always
7. encourages teachers to design innovative learning activities through the use of ICT.	4.21	Always
8. provides opportunities for teachers to acquire knowledge of modern instructional materials and instructional techniques.	4.24	Always
9. focuses on providing teachers digital skills and competencies.	4.50	Always
10. facilitates and reviews the effective use of ICT and integration of 21 st century skills in teaching and learning.	4.44	Always
Section Mean	4.47	Always

Table 10. Level of Implementation of SLAC in the Area of Curriculum Contextualization

Indicator	Mean	Description
The School Learning Action Cell....		
1. ensures that the curriculum content and instructional strategies relevant to the local contexts and student needs.	4.59	Always
2. emphasizes that the K to 12 Curriculum and Matatag Curriculum are culture-responsive, integrative, contextualized and relevant.	4.53	Always
3. develops and reviews curriculum materials to ensure contextual relevance.	4.44	Always
4. encourages the modification of lesson guides and learning materials and the use of differentiated activities to accommodate the unique contexts of a particular locality and various learning abilities of learners.	4.38	Always
5. encourages teachers to connect learning with real-world issues in their community to make students' learning experiences efficient and relevant.	4.41	Always
6. provides teachers with training and support on strategies for contextualizing curriculum such as modifying instructional materials, adapting teaching methods, and incorporating culturally sensitive topics.	4.32	Always
7. provides teachers with resources and materials to support contextualized teaching and learning.	4.24	Always
8. conducts sessions for teachers to work collaboratively by sharing their best practices on curriculum contextualization.	4.35	Always
9. encourages students participation in community-based projects and activities that reinforce contextualized learning.	4.38	Always
10. incorporates local resources into teachers' lesson plans.	4.32	Always
Section Mean	4.40	Always

Table 11. Summary of the Level Implementation of SLAC

Areas	Section Mean	Description
Content and Pedadogy	4.43	Always
Content Assessment	4.36	Always
21 st Century Skills and ICT integration	4.47	Always

Curriculum Contextualization	4.40	Always
Overall Mean	4.42	Always

Perceived Impact Of Slac Implementation On The Professional Development Of Araling Panlipunan Teachers

Table 12. Perceived impact of SLAC implementation on the Professional Development of Araling Panlipunan teachers in the area of Pedagogical competence

Indicator	Mean	Description
The School Learning Action Cell helps teachers....		
1. gain knowledge about the Matatag Curriculum and K to 12 Curriculum.	4.44	Strongly Agree
2. align teaching strategies with curriculum standards.	4.24	Strongly Agree
3. implement differentiated teaching styles to encourage critical thinking skills among my learners.	4.44	Strongly Agree
4. stay updated on recent pedagogical trends and innovations.	4.50	Strongly Agree
5. communicate effectively with my learners, especially during the teaching-learning process.	4.38	Strongly Agree
6. plan out my lessons with specific learning objectives and assessment of students' understanding.	4.56	Strongly Agree
7. use evaluative feedback to assist students in their progress.	4.12	Agree
8. handle classroom distractions and challenges.	4.41	Strongly Agree
9. assess and address my instructional weaknesses.	4.44	Strongly Agree
10. improve my lesson planning and instructional practices.	4.44	Strongly Agree
Section Mean	4.40	Strongly Agree

Table 13. Perceived Impact of SLAC Implementation in the Professional Development of Araling Panlipunan Teachers in the Area of Personal Competence

Indicator	Mean	Description
The School Learning Action Cell helps teachers....		
1. adapt to different roles, responsibilities, and contexts as an Araling Panlipunan teacher.	4.50	Strongly Agree
2. adapt teaching methods to suit diverse learning needs.	4.53	Strongly Agree
3. engage in self- reflection about my teaching practices.	3.85	Agree
4. see ambiguity and change as an opportunity to learn.	3.82	Strongly Agree
5. acknowledge the limitations of my knowledge with modesty while staying motivated to learn more.	4.29	Strongly Agree
6. be open-minded, objective, and accountable for my actions.	4.32	Strongly Agree
7. improve my classroom management skills.	4.47	Strongly Agree
8. develop effective techniques for increasing student engagements.	4.47	Strongly Agree
9. prioritize among multiple projects, tasks, and duties as an Araling Panlipunan teacher.	4.09	Agree
10. maintain a good work-life balance.	3.71	Agree
Section Mean	4.21	Strongly Agree

Table 14. Perceived Impact of SLAC Implementation in the Professional Development of Araling Panlipunan Teachers in the Area of Social Competence

Indicator	Mean	Description
The School Learning Action Cell helps teachers....		
1. enhance my skills in collaborative teamwork with my fellow teachers.	4.41	Strongly Agree
2. improve my ability to address and solve issues within the teaching team.	4.47	Strongly Agree
3. demonstrate respect for diversity among students and find ways for students to share their cultural backgrounds.	4.50	Strongly Agree
4. recognize commonalities and differences that exist among students.	4.32	Strongly Agree

5. provide opportunities for students to work together in groups or with partners.	4.41	Strongly Agree
6. model respect for others in my daily interactions with students and co-workers.	4.56	Strongly Agree
7. communicate with various stakeholders, including students, colleagues, educational staff, parents, or guardians, and maintain respectful interactions with the surrounding community.	4.41	Strongly Agree
8. develop effective techniques for increasing student engagements.	4.53	Strongly Agree
9. actively listen to colleagues and students.	4.47	Strongly Agree
10. show empathy for students and establish positive teacher-student relationships.	4.41	Strongly Agree
Section Mean	4.45	Strongly Agree

Table 15. Perceived Impact of SLAC Implementation in the Professional Development of Araling Panlipunan Teachers in the Area of Professional Competence

Indicator	Mean	Description
The School Learning Action Cell helps teachers....		
1. improve my subject- specific knowledge.	4.44	Strongly Agree
2. develop new skills that I apply in my teaching practice.	4.47	Strongly Agree
3. explain Araling Panlipunan's subject matters systematically.	4.53	Strongly Agree
4. master the core competencies and basic competencies that I will teach.	4.35	Strongly Agree
5. develop teaching materials that meet the needs of my learners.	4.44	Strongly Agree
6. undertake self-development that supports mastery of teaching materials.	4.32	Strongly Agree
7. provide students with an understanding of concepts related to teaching materials.	4.32	Strongly Agree
8. learn and improve myself, stay updated with educational research, new teaching methods and changes in curriculum standards.	4.32	Strongly Agree
9. create and maintain a positive learning environment, manage student behavior, and foster respectful relationships among my students.	4.29	Strongly Agree

10. adhere to ethical standards of the teaching profession, including integrity, fairness, and respect for student confidentiality.	4.32	Strongly Agree
Section Mean	4.39	Strongly Agree

Table 16. Summary of the Perceived Impact of SLAC Implementation on the Professional Development of Araling Panlipunan teachers.

Areas	Section Mean	Description
Pedagogical Competence	4.40	Strongly Agree
Personal Competence	4.21	Strongly Agree
Social Competence	4.45	Strongly Agree
Professional Competence	4.39	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	4.36	Strongly Agree

Difference in the level of SLAC implementation

Table 17. Analysis of the Levels of SLAC Implementation in Four (4) Areas.

Source of Variation	Df	sum of squares	Mean square	F- comp	p- value
Between	3	0.24	0.08	0.67	0.58
Within	132	16.25	0.12		
TOTAL	135				

$\alpha=0.05$ level of significance

Difference in the Impact of SLAC implementation on the Professional Development of Araling Panlipunan teachers

Table 18. Analysis of the Impact of SLAC Implementation in the Professional Development of Araling Panlipunan Teachers according to Competence.

Source of Variation	Df	sum of squares	Mean square	F- comp	p- value
Between	3	1.17	0.39	3	0.03
Within	132	17.03	0.13		
TOTAL	135	18.20			

$\alpha=0.05$ level of significance

Table 19. Separation of Means of the Four Areas of Professional Development

Components of Professional Development	Section Mean
Pedagogical Competence	4.40 ^a
Personal Competence	4.21 ^b
Social Competence	4.45 ^a
Professional Competence	4.39 ^a
Overall Mean	4.36

Relationship between the Level of SLAC Implementation on the Professional Development of Araling Panlipunan Teachers

Table 20. Analysis of the Relationship between the Level of Implementation of SLAC and its Impact on the Professional Development of Araling Panlipunan Teachers

Variables	r	p- value
Implementation of SLAC and Impact of SLAC	0.76	<0.0001

$\alpha=0.05$ level of significance

The Influence of Demographic Profile of the respondents in the Professional Development and the SLAC implementation.

Table 21. Analysis of Age and Impact of SLAC on the Professional Development of Araling Panlipunan Teachers.

Variables	R	R ²	p- value
Age or respondents and SLAC implementation	0.50	0.25	0.003

$\alpha=0.05$ level of significance

Table 22. Analysis of Sex and Impact of SLAC Implementation on the Professional Development of Araling Panlipunan Teachers

Variables	N	mean	SD	Df	t-comp.	p- value
Male	12	4.30	0.31	32	0.89	0.38
Female	22	4.39	0.28			

$\alpha=0.05$ level of significance

Table 23. Analysis of Educational Attainment and Impact SLAC Implementation on the Professional Development of Araling Panlipunan Teachers.

Source of Variation	df	sum of squares	Mean square	F-comp	p-value
Between	2	0.40	0.20	2.86	0.08
Within	31	2.32	0.07		
Total	33	2.72			

$\alpha=0.05$ level of significance

Table 24. Analysis of the Number of Years of Teaching Experience and Impact of SLAC Implementation on the Professional Development of Araling Panlipunan Teachers.

Variables	R	R ²	p- value
Length of service and SLAC implementation	0.49	0.24	0.003

$\alpha=0.05$ level of significance

Table 25. Analysis of Classroom Observation Ratings and Impact of SLAC Implementation on the Professional Development of Araling Panlipunan Teachers.

Variables	R	R ²	p- value
Classroom observation and impact of SLAC	0.48	0.23	0.004

$\alpha=0.05$ level of significance

Table 26. Summary of the significant influence of the demographic profile of the respondents on the impact of SLAC implementation on the professional development of Araling Panlipunan teachers.

Variables	p- value	Interpretation
Age	0.003	Statistically significant
Sex	0.38	Not statistically significant
Educational Attainment	0.08	Not statistically significant
Teaching Experience in Years during the SLAC Implementation	0.003	Statistically significant
Classroom Observation Rating	0.004	Statistically significant

$\alpha=0.05$ level of significance

Table 27. Analysis of Age and Implementation of SLAC

Variables	R	R²	p- value
Age and Implementation of SLAC	0.55	0.30	0.0007

$\alpha=0.05$ level of significance

Table 28. Analysis of Sex and Implementation of SLAC

Variables	n	mean	SD	Df	t-comp.	p- value
Male	12	4.37	0.29	32	0.62	0.54
Female	22	4.44	0.31			

$\alpha=0.05$ level of significance

Table 29. Analysis of Educational Attainment and Implementation of SLAC

Source of Variation	df	sum of squares	Mean square	F- comp	p- value
Between	2	0.20	0.10	1.11	0.34
Within	31	2.76	0.09		
Total	33	2.96			

$\alpha=0.05$ level of significance

Table 30. Analysis of Length of Service and Implementation of SLAC

Variables	R	R²	p- value
Length of service and SLAC implementation	0.38	0.14	0.03

$\alpha=0.05$ level of significance

Table 31. Analysis of Classroom Observation Rating and Implementation of SLAC

Variables	R	R²	p- value
Classroom observation and implementation of SLAC	0.42	0.18	0.01

$\alpha=0.05$ level of significance

Table 32. Summary of the significant influence of the demographic profile of the respondents on the implementation of SLAC.

Variables	p- value	Interpretation
Age	0.0007	Statistically significant
Sex	0.54	Not statistically significant
Educational Attainment	0.34	Not statistically significant
Teaching Experience in Years during the SLAC Implementation	0.03	Statistically significant
Classroom Observation Rating	0.001	Statistically significant

$\alpha=0.05$ level of significance

DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 2 shows that the majority of the respondents are aged 28- 32 with a percentage rate of 41%, while 9 or 26% of them belong to the 33-37 years old range, 5 or 15% of them are aged 43-47, and 4 or 12% of them belong to 38-42 years old age group. Moreover, respondents aged 48-52 and 53-57 reveal the lowest frequency of 1 or with a 3% rate. This implies that there are more secondary Araling Panlipunan Teachers I- III in Sto. Niño District, Sto. Niño, South Cotabato who are aged 28-32.

Table 3 presents that most respondents were female, 22 or 65%, compared to 12 male respondents, who had a 35% rate. This implies more female secondary Araling Panlipunan Teachers I—III in Sto. Niño District, Sto. Niño, South Cotabato.

Table 4 shows that 24 or 70% of the teacher-respondents earned Master’s Units, while 6 or 18% were Bachelor’s degree holders. Among the 34 respondents, 3 or 9% were Master’s Degree holders, while only 1 or 3% had earned Doctorate units. This implies that most respondents enroll in post-graduate programs that offer them professional development and career advancement opportunities. Teachers can improve their skills, attitudes, and knowledge through professional development opportunities, which help schools with curriculum, instruction, and assessment (Gamboa, 2023).

It can be gleaned from the table 5 that during the implementation of SLAC, 16 or 47% of the teacher-respondents rendered 8 years in service, 6 or 17% rendered 6 years, and 5 or 15% rendered 7 years in teaching. Meanwhile, 24 or 12% rendered 3 years, 2 or 6% rendered 5 years, and only 1 with the rate of 3% rendered 4 years in service. These findings imply that most respondents have participated in the SLAC sessions from its implementation through the Department of Education (DepEd) Order No. 35, series of 2016 as a K to 12 Basic Education Program and School-Based Continuing Professional Development Strategy, making them well-positioned to evaluate the impact of SLAC implementation. Darling-Hammond et al. (2017) states that more seasoned educators are better able to assess the efficacy and practicality of training programs because they have a more in-depth understanding of instruction and better reflection abilities. Their ability to

track trends and developments over time makes them reliable informants for program assessment.

As shown in table 6, the mean ratings of the respondents for all three school years are very close, with values of 4.79 for S.Y. 2021- 2022, 4.80 for S.Y. 2022- 2023, and 4.80 for S.Y. 2023- 2024. These scores based on the RPMS rating and transmutation table fall under the Outstanding category, indicating that the respondents consistently performed at a high level over the years by using well-connected pedagogical aspects of the indicator in the rating tool to create an environment that addresses individual group learning goals (DepEd Memorandum No. 004, s. 2021 & DepEd Memorandum No. 008, s. 2022). The standard deviation (SD) values range between 0.11 and 0.12 and show very little variation in the ratings, which indicates that the ratings of the respondents were closely clustered around the mean, suggesting the outstanding performance of the teachers. In addition, the consistency in high mean scores and low standard deviation (SD) across the three years suggests that Proficient teacher respondents maintained a high level of outstanding performance. Moreover, the overall section mean of 4.80 reinforces that the respondents' ratings remain outstanding across all three years. This is due to creating engaging, motivating, and supportive learning environments that increase student engagement and participation (Hattie, 2009).

Level of implementation of SLAC

Table 7 presents that the mean scores range from 4.29 to 4.59, with an overall mean of 4.43, indicating that School Learning Action (SLAC) is fully implemented in Sto. Niño secondary schools, in terms of content and pedagogy. The highest-rated indicator emphasizes that SLAC always encourages Araling Panlipunan teachers to use student-centered and inquiry-based approaches. In contrast, the lowest-rated indicator relates that SLAC assisted teachers in planning weekly Araling Panlipunan lessons, suggesting improvement. Moreover, the overall data indicates that SLAC is fully implemented in secondary schools in Sto. Niño District, Sto. Niño, South Cotabato. This is supported by the findings of Corpuz and Salandanan (2015), that collaborative discussions within professional learning communities can significantly improve instructional planning and classroom delivery. Bubb and Earley (2007) also emphasized that collaborative learning models, such as SLAC, are most effective when they are content-driven and pedagogically relevant, thereby fostering continuous improvement in teaching quality.

Table 8 presents the program's implementation level in content assessment, which is a critical component in education, ensuring that students acquire knowledge and demonstrate their understanding effectively. The mean scores for all indicators range from 4.24- 4.53, with an overall section mean of 4.36. The description states that SLAC is fully implemented in schools in terms of content assessment. The highest-rated indicator on implementing learner-centered assessment policies suggests that schools adhere to curriculum policies regarding content assessment. In contrast, the lowest rated indicator on reviewing assessments to align with learning objectives and standards indicates that SLAC implementation in schools must improve in reviewing assessments to align in learning objectives and content standards. Moreover, the consistency in high scores or ratings on indicators on setting learning targets (4.44), ensuring organized

assessments (4.41), identifying learning gaps (4.38), and planning feedback with parents (4.35) implies that schools are effectively using SLAC to track and improve student learning outcomes. The overall result indicates that SLAC is fully implemented in secondary schools in terms of assessment-related activities, effective utilization of assessment data to improve student learning, and involvement of parents in the process. The findings is consistent with the study of Magno (2021) that SLAC sessions have influenced teachers' assessment practices. The consistent high ratings in indicators like identifying learning gaps and planning with parents reflect SLAC's growing role in fostering learner-centered assessment.

It can be gleaned from table 9 that the mean scores range from 4.21 to 4.68, with an overall mean of 4.47, implying that SLAC is fully implemented in schools to promote 21st-century skills and ICT use. Indicator number 4 has the highest implementation score (4.68), which provides learning opportunities for students to foster creativity and innovation. This suggests that schools highly prioritize using SLAC to support creativity and innovation among teachers. On the other hand, indicator 7 has the lowest implementation score (4.21), encouraging teachers to design innovative learning activities through ICT. This implies some challenges in fully integrating ICT-based innovative learning activities. Moreover, SLAC performed strongly in key areas such as teaching 21st-century skills as part of the curriculum, encouraging problem-solving and decision-making strategies, and promoting group work and collaboration, with a mean score of 4.59. This result is closely associated with Reyes & Tamayo concept that SLAC sessions were seen as vital in enhancing teachers' ability to implement learner-centered approaches, use collaborative methods, and integrate 21st-century skills into daily lessons.

Table 10 presents the mean scores range from 4.24 to 4.59, with an overall section mean of 4.40. This implies that SLAC is fully implemented in schools to promote curriculum relevance, modification, real-world connections, and collaborative teacher learning. The highest-rated indicator (4.59) states that SLAC ensures curriculum content and instructional strategies are relevant to local content and students' needs, suggesting that SLAC is highly effective in adapting teaching to local requirements. Meanwhile, the lowest-rated indicator (4.24) relates to providing teachers with resources and materials to support contextualized teaching and learning, suggesting that while SLAC is fully implemented in curriculum contextualization, there may be gaps in resource availability for teachers. The result is consistent with the findings of Santos and Abad (2021) that SLAC has been pivotal in developing collaborative professional learning communities within schools, contributing to the overall development of teachers' skills in modifying and adapting the curriculum to meet student needs.

As presented in the table 11, 21st Century Skills and ICT integration topped the list of areas of SLAC that is always implemented in schools with a mean of 4.47. Content and Pedagogy came very closely with a mean of 4.43. The mean of 4.40 for Curriculum Contextualization and 4.36 for Content Assessment also imply that there is consistent practice and implementation of SLAC on the said areas. Overall, data reveal that the SLAC activities in all areas were fully implemented in schools with the overall mean of 4.42.

Perceived impact of SLAC implementation in the professional development

The data analysis in table 12 shows that the SLAC had a very strong impact on the professional development of Araling Panlipunan teachers as perceived by the respondents, as shown by the mean score range of 4.12 to 4.56 and the section mean of 4.40. The highest-rated indicator, 4.56, states that SLAC helps teachers plan their lessons with specific learning objectives and assessments of students' understanding. This signifies that SLAC is highly effective in helping teachers design structured, goal-oriented lessons. Furthermore, another strong area of SLAC, with a rate of 4.50, is that it helps teachers stay updated on recent pedagogical trends and innovations, showing that SLAC supports teachers in keeping up with modern teaching practices. On the other hand, using evaluative feedback to assist students in their progress is the lowest-rated indicator, with a rating of 4.12. This suggests that SLAC must support teachers in effectively using student feedback to improve. The professional learning communities like SLAC are known to foster reflective practice, enhance instructional strategies, and improve student learning outcomes through teacher collaboration (Avalos, 2011; Opfer & Pedder, 2011).

As shown in the data in table 13, the respondents strongly agree that the SLAC had a very strong impact on their personal competence. This can be reflected in the mean score range of 3.71 to 4.53 and the section mean of 4.21, which indicates a generally positive perception of the SLAC's effectiveness in improving teachers' skills and competence. The highest-rated indicators, 4.53 and 4.47, relate to adapting teaching methods and classroom management, while the lowest-rated indicators, 3.71 and 3.85, concern teachers' work-life balance and self-reflection. The results further indicate that SLAC is most effective in enhancing teaching adaptability, classroom management, and student engagement but must focus more on the needed self-reflection, adaptability, and assistance in time management and prioritization of teachers. This was closely associated with Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs (1943) and Banduras' Self-Efficacy Theory (1997), which states that if teachers' personal needs are being met, this will affect their motivation, behavior, and overall teaching effectiveness.

As presented in table 14, the section mean is 4.45, and the mean score ranges from 4.32 to 4.56. This indicates that the Araling Panlipunan teachers strongly agree that SLAC had very strong impact on their Social competence as teachers. The highest-rated indicator, 4.56, shows that SLAC had a very strong impact on how teachers model respect for others in daily interactions, which implies teachers' professionalism and respect. The lowest-rated indicator is the impact of SLAC on how teachers recognize commonalities and differences among students, which suggests that SLAC must focus on diversity awareness. The findings are similar to the claim of Garcia & Navarro (2020) that SLAC had a very strong impact on teachers' social competence as it promoted collaborative learning, communication, and the ability to work effectively in teams. Teachers reported improvements in their confidence to engage in peer-to-peer interactions, share teaching strategies, and address collective challenges, all of which contributed to a more supportive and cohesive school environment.

Table 15 presents data on the perceived impact of SLAC implementation on the Professional development of teachers in the area of Professional competence. Like other areas of Professional Development, the SLAC had a very strong impact on the Professional competence of Araling Panlipunan teachers, as reflected in the mean score range of 4.29 to 4.53 and the section mean of 4.39. The indicators with the highest score of 4.53 show that SLAC had helped teachers explain their subject matter systematically, developing skills for teaching practice with a 4.47 rate, and improving subject-specific knowledge. On the other hand, indicators with relatively lower scores are creating a positive learning environment with a 4.29 rate and undertaking self-development for mastering teaching materials with 4.32. The findings show that SLAC strongly improved subject knowledge, teaching strategies, and systematic instruction. In contrast, the impact on ethical standards and self-development was slightly lower yet remains highly significant. This is similar to the study of Manalo (2023), that more frequent LAC sessions led to higher teaching competencies which confirms that LAC is essential for collaboration, professional development and continuous learning among teachers.

Table 16 summarizes the results of the impact of SLAC implementation on the Professional Development of Araling Panlipunan teachers in areas of Pedagogical Competence, Personal Competence, Social Competence and Professional Competence. As shown and as perceived by the respondents the SLAC implementation had a very strong impact on their Professional Development in four areas. The overall mean of 4.36 implies that the high level of SLAC implementation in Sto. Niño district had a very strong impact on the Professional Development of Araling Panlipunan teachers helping them in them improve their Pedagogical, Personal, Social and Professional Competence. This is similar to the findings of Culajara (2023) that there is a statistically significant increase in teacher self-efficacy after participating in SLAC sessions and activities. Moreover, Aquino et al. (2023) also found out that collaborative problem-solving through SLAC sessions positively influences professional competence of teachers.

Difference in the level of SLAC implementation

The fourth research problem investigates possible differences in the implementation of SLAC in terms of content and pedagogy, content assessment, 21st-century skills, ICT integration in teaching Araling Panlipunan, and curriculum contextualization, as rated by the respondents. The study's findings are shown in Table 17. Since F-computed is 0.67 with a p-value of 0.58, which is greater than $\alpha=0.05$, the variation among means of the four areas of implementation is due to chance. The level of SLAC implementation in content and pedagogy is as good as in content assessment, 21st-century skills and ICT integration, and curriculum contextualization. The results then imply that the differences in SLAC implementation across the four areas are insignificant, and the school's implementation is relatively consistent. Andaya (2020) highlighted that no significant disparity in the quality of implementation across these domains, suggests balanced support for teacher competencies through SLAC.

Difference in the Impact of SLAC implementation on the Professional Development of Araling Panlipunan teachers.

The fifth research problem analyzes the impact of SLAC on the professional development of Araling Panlipunan teachers in the areas of pedagogical competence, personal competence, social competence, and professional competence. Tables 18 and 19 illustrate the study's findings. Since F -computed is 3 with a p -value of 0.03, which is less than $\alpha=0.05$, the variation among means of impact of SLAC implementation classified into four professional development components is greater than expected by chance. It implies that SLAC affects different competencies in professional development to varying degrees. The analysis is extended using the Tukey—Kramer Multiple Comparison Test to determine which professional development component impacts SLAC implementation more. Social competence has the highest mean rating (4.45) on the impact of SLAC implementation, comparable to social and professional competence. However, personal competence has a lower mean rating (4.21), which is too different from the rest of the professional development components suggesting it is less impacted by SLAC implementation and needs further improvement and focus.

. The findings are also consistent with the study of Antiola and Ferenal (2024), that SLAC has a significant positive impact on teachers' instructional skills which are closely related to professional competence but has no strong effect on teachers' personal competence.

Relationship between the Level of SLAC Implementation on the Professional Development of Araling Panlipunan Teachers

The sixth research problem concerns the relationship between the SLAC implementation level and its perceived impact, as shown in Table 20. The data analysis shows that since $r=0.76$ (strong relationship) with p -value = <0.0001 , it is less than enough to claim that $r = 0.76$ is greater than expected by chance. This implies that SLAC is an effective professional development strategy, and the higher SLAC implementation results in greater professional benefits for teachers. The finding is similar to the claims of Reyes et al. (2017) and Sanchez et al. (2018) that SLAC effectiveness was correlated with higher levels of pedagogical efficacy among teachers and SLAC participation was associated with improved instructional mastery, professional development, and teaching practices.

The Influence of Demographic Profile of the respondents in the Professional Development and the SLAC implementation.

The seventh research problem deals with finding out the significant influence of the demographic profile of the respondents on their Professional development and SLAC implementation. Tables 21 to 32 provide the complete data for the research problem.

Table 21 analyzes the influence of age on the impact of SLAC on the professional development of Araling Panlipunan teachers. The data shows a moderate positive relationship between age and the impact of SLAC, as represented by $r=0.50$ and a p -

value of 0.003. This suggests that as teachers' age, they tend to experience a greater impact from SLAC implementation on their professional development. The r-squared (R^2) is the coefficient of determination, represented by 0.25 (25%). It revealed that around twenty-five percent (25%) of the variation in ratings on the impact of SLAC is attributed to the respondents' age, and other factors influence the remaining 75%. The outcomes corroborate Sanchez et al. (2018) discoveries that age moderately affected teachers' satisfaction with SLAC implementation and its impact on their professional development.

Table 22 presents the data on the analysis of the significant influence of the respondents' sex and the impact of SLAC on the professional development of Araling Panlipunan teachers. The data analysis implies that since the t-computed is 0.89 and the p-value is 0.38, the difference between the means of males and females on ratings of the impact of SLAC is due to chance. The standard deviation (SD) of 0.31 for male and 0.28 for female respondents connotes that both groups show a low spread of data and their responses are consistent. Moreover, it means that sex does not influence respondents' perception of the impact of SLAC implementation on their professional development, and SLAC implementation affects both male and female teachers equally. It aligns with the study of Krosnick (2018) that sex differences in survey responses were minimal and often non-significant, suggesting that sex does not significantly influence the responses.

As shown in table 23, the F-computed is 2.86 with a p-value of 0.08, which indicates that the difference among means of ratings on the impact of SLAC implementation classified according to the respondents' educational attainment is due to chance. Thus, educational attainment does not have an impact on SLAC implementation. Sanchez et al. (2018) found that educational attainment was not a significant predictor of teacher responses to a survey on SLAC implementation, suggesting that educational attainment does not significantly influence responses. Furthermore, the SLAC implementation appears equally effective across different educational levels.

The data analysis in table 24 reveals a moderate positive relationship between the length of service and the impact of SLAC, as represented by $r=0.49$ with a p-value of 0.003. The r-squared (R^2) is the coefficient of determination represented by 0.24 (24%). It revealed that around twenty-four percent (24%) of the variation in ratings on the impact of SLAC is attributed to the length of service of the respondents. The results also indicate that experienced teachers may benefit more from SLAC programs due to their ability to integrate new learning with prior experience and that younger or less experienced teachers might require additional support to maximize SLAC's benefits. Rockoff (2004) supports this, stating that experienced teachers might provide more informed or nuanced responses due to their accumulated knowledge and experience.

Table 25 displays data analysis on the classroom observation ratings and the impact of SLAC implementation on the Professional development of Araling Panlipunan teachers. Since the correlation coefficient is $(r)=0.48$, with a p-value of 0.004, teachers' ratings on classroom observation have a positive and moderate relationship with ratings on the impact of SLAC implementation. The influence of classroom observation on the ratings on the impact of SLAC implementation is (R^2) 0.23. This means that around 23% of the variation in the ratings on the impact of SLAC implementation is attributed to

classroom observation and other factors influence the remaining 77%. This result suggests that teachers with higher observation ratings may be engaged in SLAC activities and apply their learnings more effectively. SLAC training might also reinforce good teaching practices, improving classroom performance. A study by Brawner et al. (2019) also found that classroom observation ratings were a significant outcome of SLAC implementation, with teachers who participated in SLAC showing improvement in their teaching practices.

As presented in table 26, the age of the respondents with p- value of (0.003), teaching experience in years during the SLAC implementation (p- value of 0.003), and their Classroom observation ratings (p- value of 0.004) has significant influence on the impact of SLAC implementation on the professional development of Araling Panlipunan teachers. These variables likely play key roles on how SLAC contributes to the teachers' professional development.

Table 27-32 presents the data analysis on the influence of the age of respondents and the implementation of SLAC.

As revealed in the data from table 27, the relationship between age and the ratings on the SLAC implementation level is positive at 0.55. There is a moderate relationship between age and level of implementation of SLAC. This indicates that older teachers tend to have a higher SLAC implementation level than younger teachers. The coefficient of determination is 0.30. It shows that around thirty percent (30%) of the variation in the ratings on the implementation of SLAC is attributed to the age of the respondents, and other factors influence the remaining 70%. According to Guskey (2002), experienced teachers value continuous learning and professional development initiatives like SLAC.

Table 28 presents that since the t-computed is 0.62 and the p-value is 0.54, the difference between male and female means on rating implementation of SLAC is due to chance. This means that sex does not influence the perception of respondents about the implementation of SLAC. The results align with the study of DuFour and Eaker (1998), which states that perceptions of implementation effectiveness are more likely influenced by factors such as culture, leadership support, and prior experience rather than sex or gender.

Table 29 also presents that since the F-computed is 1.11 with a p-value of 0.34, the difference among the means of ratings on the implementation of SLAC, which is classified according to the respondents' educational attainment, is due to chance. Thus, the respondents' educational attainment has no influence on the implementation of SLAC. Research by Guskey (2002) supports these findings, indicating that teacher development programs are effective across different levels of educational attainment as long as professional support and engagement are maintained. Furthermore, Lave and Wenger (1991) support the findings that learning is more effective in a social context where all individuals contribute regardless of educational background. Since SLAC functions as a collaborative learning system, its implementation depends on participation and support rather than the participants' educational attainment.

Table 30 reflects the analysis of respondents' length of service or teaching experience and the implementation of SLAC. 05 level of significance. Data reveal that the degree of relationship between the length of service and SLAC implementation level based on the Correlation coefficient (r) is 0.38. It is a positive and moderate degree of relationship. It implies that respondents with a higher length of service may likely give high ratings on the implementation of SLAC. The influence of length service is quantified by r -squared = 0.14. This implies that around fourteen percent (14%) of the variation in the level of implementation of SLAC is attributed to the length of service of the respondents. In comparison, eighty-six percent (86%) is influenced by other factors (Avalos, 2011). The findings align with studies emphasizing the role of experience in professional learning and collaboration. Teachers with longer service tend to be more engaged in professional learning communities and are more likely to appreciate the benefits of SLAC in improving instructional practices (Garet et al., 2001). Similarly, Darling-Hammond et al. (2017) emphasize that teacher collaboration and leadership improve with experience, which can enhance the implementation of programs like SLAC.

Table 31 presents data on the analysis of classroom observation ratings of the Araling Panlipunan teachers and the implementation of SLAC. Since $r=0.42$ and a p -value of 0.01, teachers' classroom observation ratings have a positive and moderate relationship with ratings of SLAC implementation. The influence of classroom observation on the ratings of implementing SLAC is 0.18. This means that around 18% of the variation in the ratings on implementing SLAC is attributed to classroom observation. These results align with those of Manzano et al. (2011), who found that when teachers conduct thorough classroom observations, they can better assess their students' progress and adjust their teaching methods. This, in turn, affects professional learning communities like SLAC.

As presented in table 32, the age of the respondents with p - value of (0.0007), teaching experience in years during the SLAC implementation (p - value of 0.03), and their Classroom observation ratings (p - value 0.001) has significant influence on the impact of SLAC implementation on the professional development of Araling Panlipunan teachers. These variables likely play key roles on how SLAC was implemented in schools. On the other hand, the sex and educational experiences of the respondents does not influence the SLAC implementation in school.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were drawn in light of the findings and the hypothesis that was put to the test.

1. The demographic profile of the respondents indicates a group of highly qualified and experienced educators. Their consistent participation in SLAC sessions over the span of eight years (2016–2024) reflects a strong commitment to continuous professional development. The outstanding classroom observation ratings

sustained over the last three school years further underscore their teaching competence and instructional effectiveness.

2. Secondary schools in Sto. Niño District, Sto. Niño, South Cotabato, has effectively and fully implemented the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) program in terms of content and pedagogy, content assessment, the integration of technology and 21st-century skills, and the contextualization of the curriculum.
3. SLAC had a very strong impact on the professional development of Araling Panlipunan teachers in terms of pedagogical, personal, social, and professional competencies.
4. The differences in SLAC implementation across the four areas are insignificant and the school's program implementation is relatively consistent.
5. There is a significant difference in its impact on teachers' professional development, with personal competence showing the lowest mean compared to other competencies yet it remains to be significant.
6. The results also indicate a strong positive relationship between SLAC implementation and its impact on teachers' professional development. This demonstrates that a higher level of SLAC implementation corresponds to greater improvements in teachers' competencies.
7. The impact of SLAC Implementation and its effects on Professional development are heavily influenced by demographic parameters, including age, teaching experience, and outstanding classroom observation ratings.
8. Overall, this study affirms that SLAC is an effective professional development program that enhances the teaching quality and professional competencies of Araling Panlipunan teachers.

Recommendations

In light of the conclusion mentioned above, the following are the recommendations:

1. Given the respondents' strong professional qualifications majority having master's degree and their consistent participation in SLAC (School Learning Action Cell) sessions over an extended period (2016–2024), it is recommended that this group be tapped as peer mentors or facilitators in future professional development initiatives. Their sustained engagement in the SLAC program, paired with their excellent classroom observation ratings indicates a high level of teaching competence and reflective practice. By positioning them in mentorship roles, schools can promote a culture of collaborative learning and capacity-building within the teaching community.
2. Noting that SLAC is fully implemented in secondary schools, it can be suggested that schools may strengthen and ensure the continuous implementation of SLAC sessions focusing on content and pedagogy, content assessment, 21st-century skills and ICT integration, and curriculum contextualization. School administrators may also provide adequate time, resources, and support to sustain the SLAC implementation.
3. As found out, the SLAC implementation had a strong impact on the professional development of Araling Panlipunan teachers, especially in terms of pedagogical, social, and professional competence. Thus, it is recommended to continue

implementing the SLAC as a regular and structured professional development program in all secondary schools by continue providing capacity-building seminars, collaborative learning and networking sessions, parent-teacher engagement strategies, innovative teaching methods workshops, and leadership development programs for all teachers to further enhance their skills and knowledge.

4. Since the analysis revealed that there is no significant difference in the level of SLAC implementation across the four key areas of content and pedagogy, content assessment, 21st-century skills and CT integration, and curriculum contextualization it is recommended that the current implementation strategies be maintained and possibly standardized across all areas.
5. Based on the results, the impact of SLAC implementation on the Personal Competence of Araling Panlipunan teachers is slightly lower yet remains highly significant. Therefore, SLAC sessions are recommended to integrate self-reflection activities, confidence-building exercises, stress management techniques, and similar activities that promote teachers' overall well-being. SLAC can also be more effective if it includes mentorship programs and peer support to encourage teacher participants and boost their confidence.
6. With the strong relationship between SLAC and the professional development of Araling Panlipunan teachers, it is suggested that there is a regular evaluation. The evaluation findings will be useful in refining and improving the SLAC implementation, ensuring that it supports teachers' professional development and students' learning outcomes. SLAC leaders may also work on the Professional Regulatory Commission (PRC) Accreditation of their SLAC activities through the Continuing Professional Development System (CPDAS) to ensure that they continue to meet standards for teacher competency development.
7. Considering the significant influence of the age, teaching experience, and outstanding classroom observation ratings of the respondents on the SLAC implementation and its impact on the Professional Development of Araling Panlipunan teachers, SLAC sessions may also include age-specific professional development opportunities that would cater to the unique needs and interests of different age groups. It is also better to strengthen the mentorship program through SLAC, where experienced teachers and teachers with outstanding observation ratings can support or guide other colleagues.
8. Further research and evaluation are recommended to assess the long-term impact of SLAC and validate the study's results.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

After finding out that the research instrument was valid and reliable, a letter was made to the Dean of the Graduate School seeking permission to conduct the study. The same request letter was sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of South Cotabato. The approved letter of request was attached to the letter for the District Supervisor and School Principals of five public secondary schools in the municipality of Sto. Niño, South Cotabato regarding the purpose. A courtesy call was made regarding the mechanics of administering the survey questionnaire. After getting the approval of the public school district supervisor and the school heads to conduct the study under their jurisdiction, the

research instruments were then distributed. The respondents were oriented on answering the survey questionnaires and were given ample time to accomplish the research instrument. The respondents were assured that their participation in the study is voluntary and could withdraw anytime without consequence. The respondents also signed a data privacy form allowing the researcher to gather data on their Classroom Observation Ratings.

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REFERENCES

- Abrol, H. S. (2021). *Statistics 404: Sampling Theory*. Directorate of Distance Education, University of Jammu.
- Andaya, O. J. F. (2020). School learning action cell (SLAC) as a key support mechanism for teachers' professional development. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 9(5), 77-86.
- Antiola, M. & Ferenal, E. (2024). Impact of school learning action cell program on teachers' instructional competence in Misamis Oriental: basis for professional development plan. *American Journal of Arts and Human Science*, 3(3), 116-149. <https://doi.org/10.54536/ajahs.v3i3.3021>
- Aquino, S., Kilag, O. Cordova Jr., N. & Branzuela, J. (2023). Transformative learning: a deep dive into SLAC sessions and teacher empowerment. *Excellencia: International Multi- Disciplinary Journal of Education*, 1(5), 498- 509.
- Avalos, B. (2011). Teacher professional development in teaching and teacher education over ten years. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 27(1), 10-20.
- Bandura, A. (1977). *Social learning theory*. Prentice Hall
- Binauhan, R. (2019). Learning action cell implementation in the public elementary schools in the division of Cavite. *International Journal of Advanced Research and Publications*. 3(11), 27-33. <https://www.ijarp.org/published-research-papers/nov2019/Learning-Action-Cell-Implementation-In-The-Public-Elementary-Schools-In-The-Division-Of-Cavite.pdf>.
- Bubb, S., & Earley, P. (2007). *Leading and managing continuing professional development: Developing people, developing schools*. SAGE Publications.

- Clarete, P., Mondejar, M., Quimba, N. & Gaygay Jr., F. (2023). A descriptive-correlational study on personality traits and entrepreneurial intentions of senior high school learners. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*. 4(12), 4460-4472. <https://doi.org/10.11594/ijmaber.04.12.22>
- Corpuz, B. B., & Salandanan, G. G. (2015). *Principles of teaching 1* (3rd ed.). Lorimar Publishing, Inc.
- Creswell, J. W. & Creswell, J. D. (2017). *Research design qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (4th Edition). Sage, Newbury Park.
- Creswell, J. W. & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th Edition). Sage Publications.
- Culajara, C. (2023). Improving teachers' professional development through school learning action cell (SLAC). *Excellencia: International Multi- Disciplinary Journal of Education*, 1(5), 498- 509. <https://multijournals.org/index.php/excellencia-imje/article/view/148>.
- Darling- Hammond, L. Hyler, M. & Gardner, M. (2017). *Effective teacher professional development*. Learning Policy Institute.
- Deala, M. & Lopez, E. (2024). School learning action cell (SLAC) implementation and its impact on the personal and professional development among elementary teachers. *Psychology and Education: a Multidisciplinary Journal*, 21(3), 253-265. <https://scimatic.org/storage/journals/11/pdfs/3123.pdf>
- Delos Santos, J. (2023). School learning action cell and competencies of elementary teachers. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 12(6), 95-101. <https://doi.org/10.5861/ijrse.2023.40>
- DepEd Memorandum No. 004, s. 2022. Implementation of the results- based performance management system- Philippine professional standards for teachers for school year 2021- 2022.
- DepEd Memorandum No. 008, s. 2023. Multi- year guidelines on the results- based performance management system- Philippine professional standards for teachers.
- Department of Education (DepEd), Republic of the Philippines. (2016). DepEd Order No. 35, s. 2016: The learning action cell as a K to 12 basic education program school- based continuing professional development strategy for the improvement of teaching and learning. https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2016/06/DO_s2016_035.pdf
- DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015. Policy guidelines on classroom assessment for the K to 12 basic education program.
- Department of Education (DepEd), Republic of the Philippines. (2024). DepEd Order No. 014, s. 2024: Policy guidelines on the implementation of the Matatag curriculum. https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/DO_s2024_010.pdf.
- Department of Education (DepEd), Republic of the Philippines. (2023). DepEd Order No. 14, s. 2023: Policy guidelines on the implementation of the national learning camp. https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/DO_s2023_014.pdf
- DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015. Policy guidelines on classroom assessment for the K to 12 basic education program. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2015/01/30/do-8-s-2015->

- policy-guidelines-on-classroom-assessment-for-the-k-to-12-basic-education-program/
- DuFour, R. & Eaker, R. (1998). Professional learning communities at work: best practices for enhancing student achievement. Solution Tree Press.
- Garcia, L. S., & Navarro, E. D. (2020). The impact of school learning action cell (SLAC) on teachers' social competence and collaborative practices. *Educational Research Journal*, 14(2), 27–40. <https://doi.org/10.1177/edres/2020/14/2>
- Field, A. (2013). *Discovering Statistics Using IBM SPSS Statistics* (4th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Gamboa. (2023). Implementation of school learning action cell (SLAC) and its monitoring and evaluation strategies employed by teachers and school heads in the division of Occidental Mindoro, Philippines. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 4(11), 2157- 2161. <https://doi.org/10.55248/gengpi.4.1123.113119>
- Garcia, L. S., & Navarro, E. D. (2020). The impact of school learning action cell (SLAC) on teachers' social competence and collaborative practices. *Educational Research Journal*, 14(2), 27–40. <https://doi.org/10.1177/edres/2020/14/>
- Garet, M., Porter, A., Desimone, L. Birman, B., & Yoon, K. (2001). What makes professional development effective? *American Educational Research Journal*, 38(4), 915-945.
- Gustey T. (2000). *Evaluating professional development*. Corwin Press.
- Guskey T. (2002). Professional development and teacher change. *Teachers and Teaching*, 8(3), 381- 391.
- Guskey, T. (2005). Formative classroom assessment and Benjamin S. Bloom theory, research and implications. University of Kentucky, Lexington. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED490412.pdf>
- Hattie, J. (2009). *Visible learning: a synthesis of over 800 meta- analyses relating to achievement*. Routledge.
- Krosnick, J. & Fabrigar L. (1997). Survey Measurement and Process Quality. In L. Lyberg, P. Biemer, M. Collins, E. de Leeuw, C. Dippo, N. Schwrz, & D. Trewin (Eds.) *Survey measurement and process quality*. New York: John Willey
- Krosnick, J. (2018). Survey research methods. *Journal of Survey Statistics and Methodology*, 6(1), 1-15. <https://doi/10.1093/jssam/smx015>.
- Magno, C. (2021). School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) implementation and its impact on assessment practices of teachers. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 15(4), 12–22. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajess/2021/v15i430382>
- Manalo, J. D. (2023). Learning action cell as a channel for teacher’s professional competence in elementary schools in the divisions of Laguna. *Education Policy and Development*, 1(2), 40-52. <https://doi.org/10.31098/epd.v1i2.1590>, 1(2), 40–52.
- Manzano, R., Frontier, T., & Livingston, D. (2011). *Effective supervision: supporting the art and science of teaching*. ASCD.
- Maslow, A. (1943). A theory of human motivation. *Psychological Review*, 50(4). 370-396. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0054346>.

- Opfer, V. & Pedder, D. (2011). Conceptualizing teacher professional learning. *Review of Educational Research*, 81(3), 376-407.
<https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654311413609>.
- Republic of the Philippines. (2013). Republic Act No. 10533: The enhanced basic education act of 2013. *Official Gazette*.
<https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2013/05/15/republic-act-no-10533/>
- Reyes, M. C., & Tamayo, D. L. (2020). The role of School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) in enhancing 21st century teaching practices. *International Journal of Education, Learning and Development*, 8(5), 35–49.
- Rockoff, J. (2004). The impact of individual teachers on student achievement: evidence from panel data. *American Economic Review*, 94(2), 91-114.
- Salaria, Neeru. (2012). Meaning of the term- descriptive survey research method. *International Journal of Transformations in Business Management*, 1 (6).1-7.
<https://www.scirp.org>
- Santos, J. M., & Abad, M. R. (2021). The impact of school learning action cell (SLAC) on teacher professional development and curriculum innovation. *Journal of Teacher Education and Practice*, 12(3), 89–101.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/jept/2021/12/3>
- Sanchez, R., Sanchez M. & Brawner C. (2018). The impact of school learning action cell (SLAC) on teacher pedagogical efficacy. *Ascendens Asia Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Abstracts*, 4(1). 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.55053/aa-jmra.2018.v4i1.1>
- Suri, K. (2016). Teaching as a lifelong process of learning. *Daily Excelsior*.
<https://www.dailyexcelsior.com/teaching-as-a-lifelong-process-of-learning/>
- Yusoff, M. (2019). ABC of content validation and content validity index calculation. *Education in Medicine Journal*, 11(2). 49-54.
[https://doi.org/10.21315/eimj2019.11.2.6`](https://doi.org/10.21315/eimj2019.11.2.6)
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